

Synthesis of zero valent iron nanoparticles and application to removal of arsenic(III) and arsenic(V) from water

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Abstract : Recently nano scale zero valent iron particles (nZVI) have been considered as smart adsorbent for environmental and groundwater remediation. Although several synthetic methods are available for the preparation of nZVI, air stable nZVI are not available for remediation works. Further, challenges demand synthesis of nZVI without stabilizers and capping agents. A modified methodology for the synthesis of air stable nZVI has been developed without any capping agents and characterized by powder X-Ray Diffraction (XRD), Scanning Electron Microscopy Energy-dispersive X-Ray (SEM-EDS), Transmission Electron Microscopy (TEM) and X-Ray Photoelectron Spectroscopy (XPS). The results of the present study suggest that the synthetic nZVI are air-stable over a period of one year and consists of particles of 30–40 nm in diameter. Although a layer of less than 3 nm thick oxide/hydroxide is observed by TEM and XPS, it appears to be due to oxidation of outer surface during analysis. Adsorption study has shown that the synthetic nZVI are more effective adsorbent than the commercial nZVI and can remove simultaneously arsenite [As^{III}] and arsenate [As^V] from water without prior reduction of As^V to As^{III}. The removal process is adsorptive rather than precipitative and the removal of As^{III} is greater than that of As^V.

Keywords : Synthetic nZVI, powder XRD, TEM, XPS, SEM-EDS, adsorption, removal, As^{III}, As^V.

Introduction

In recent decades, extensive studies showed that zero valent iron nanoparticles (nZVI) were effective and useful for removal of various pollutants commonly present in groundwater such as perchloroethene (PCE), trichloroethene (TCE), carbon tetrachloride (CT), nitrate, energetic munitions such as trinitrotoluene (TNT) and 1,3,5-trinitroperhydro-1,3,5-triazine (RDX), legacy organohalogen pesticides such as lindane and dichlorodiphenyltrichloroethane (DDT), as well as heavy

metals like Pb, Pb^{II}, As^{III}, As^V, Cu^{II}, Ni^{II} and Cr^{VI} 1–13.

Different techniques for the stabilization of nZVI particles were available^{14,15} but synthesis of air stable nZVI was a challenging task without a stabilizer/capping agent. When nZVI particles came in contact with air during synthesis it underwent ignition forming brown iron oxides. So prevention of aerial ignition to get at zero valent state was a demanding task. Even though a large number of methods had been known for the synthesis of nZVI^{16,17–22}, borohydride reduction method was considered to be the best.

There were several methods with and without stabilizers available in the literature^{16,17-22}. In the present study the synthetic method reported by Sun *et al.*¹⁶ was tried to adopt for the adsorbent nZVI. Although the synthesized particles were stored in 5% ethanol elsewhere¹⁶, it was found difficult to store and work using it due to its less stability in ambient conditions. Later on the synthetic method described by Lin *et al.*²² was tried for the preparation of air stable nZVI and the particles formed were washed with ethanol and dried in vacuum overnight. It was observed that when the particles were taken out from the vacuum to normal condition, they started ignited and all the particles turned to brownish colour. Afterwards modified drying step of the synthesis process given by Uzum *et al.*²⁰ reported by Lin *et al.*²² was used in the present study and the particles were taken in watch glass, dried in a hot air oven at 75 °C overnight as described by Uzum *et al.*²⁰. The result did not agree with Uzum *et al.*²⁰ and the particles ignited immediately and turned to brownish colour. Finally, the synthetic method of Choi *et al.*²¹ was tried and it was found that nZVI particles synthesised was air stable for a few days. To overcome all these problems, the present study provided a simple method for the synthesis of nZVI without using any capping agents and stabilized in cold conditions.

The objective of the present study was (i) to synthesize air stable nZVI without using any surfactant or capping agent, (ii) to characterize by powder XRD, BET, TEM, SEM-EDS and XPS analysis, (iii) to check removal efficiencies of the synthesized nZVI to both As^{III} and As^V in aqueous systems without using any reducing agent and (iv) to compare its efficiency with commercial nZVI.

Results and discussion

Although nZVI black powder was purchased commercially from China (Details in reagent section) which had 25 nm average particle size, 40–60 m²/g specific surface area and bulk density of 0.10–0.25 g/cm³, fresh nZVI was synthesized in the present project by using modified procedure mentioned in Experimental section. The progress of reduction was monitored by UV-Vis spectrometry at λ_{\max} 302 nm as well as colour change from brown to black (data not shown). The nZVI particles were sonicated for at least 6–8 h before UV-Vis studies in order to obtain homogeneous colloidal iron solution.

Powder X-Ray Diffraction (XRD) study :

Powder X-Ray Diffraction (XRD) technique was used to characterize the crystallographic structure, crystallite size (grain size), and preferred orientation in polycrystalline or powdered solid samples. Fig. 1 shows XRD pattern of nZVI which was recorded over a 2 θ range of 10–90°. The peak appearing at 2 θ value of 44.71° which matches the value for Fe⁰ reported in JCPDS (00-006-0696), confirming the formation of nano iron in zero valent state. These findings support exactly the results reported elsewhere^{4,22,24-29}.

The present result (Fig. 1) confirmed exclusively zero valent state of iron nanoparticles (Fe⁰) with single-phase cubic closest-packed structure, whereas others^{9,21,30} re-

Fig. 1. Representative powder XRD pattern of synthesized nZVI.

ported the presence of polycrystalline amorphous iron(III) oxide/hydroxide, magnetite (Fe₃O₄), and/or maghemite (γ -Fe₂O₃), and lepidocrocite (γ -FeOOH) along with Fe⁰ indicating the formation of Fe^{II} as an intermediate step in the nZVI corrosion process^{29,30}. In the present study Fig. 1 does not show any peak for Fe^{II}/Fe^{III}-oxides which clearly shows that all iron nanoparticles were in zero valent state.

Transmission Electron Microscopy (TEM) study :

Fig. 2 shows image of nZVI taken by Transmission Electron Microscopy (TEM) after one year of storage at ambient condition and the small spherical particles consisted of a nearly single-crystal Fe⁰ core with a polycrystalline oxide shell. Although core-shell structure was not visible by powder X-ray diffractograms (Fig. 1), it was

Fig. 2. TEM image of synthesized nZVI.

evident in TEM images because oxidation of iron-core during TEM analysis of the specified sample occurred. Choi *et al.*²¹ reported a very thin oxide layer (1 to 2 nm) covering core iron by examining TEM image of freshly prepared nZVI. Nurmi *et al.*¹⁶ found that nZVI powders (having < 1.5-nm crystals) were aggregated into approximately spherical 20 to 100 nm diameter particles, which were ultimately aggregated into the chains and further linked into clusters of chains as shown in Fig. 2.

Others^{16,25} also reported similar chain-like aggregates of nZVI. Further, Martin *et al.*³¹ estimated the shell thickness of fresh nZVI predominantly in the range of 2–4 nm. Finally, Scherer's equation [$\tau = (K\lambda)/(\beta\cos\theta)$] was applied to XRD results and the ordered (crystalline) domains, which may be smaller or equal to the grain size was determined to be 13 ± 3 nm considering shape factor (K) as 0.9, λ as 1.54 Å, β as 0.663° (0.011571533 rad) and θ as 22.355 whereas the particle size of nZVI was 35–40 nm. This result clearly indicated that a few grains were aggregated to form a particle of about 30–40 nm in diameter (Fig. 2).

X-Ray Photoelectron Spectroscopy (XPS) study :

X-Ray Photoelectron Spectroscopy (XPS) study was carried out to get information on surface composition of one year old nanoparticles. Fig. 3 showed the photoelectron peaks at around 717.1 eV ($\text{Fe}^{2+} 2p_{3/2}$) and 729.6 eV ($\text{Fe}^{2+} 2p_{1/2}$) that suggested the presence of iron oxides (Fe-O_x) on the nZVI surface which was supported by others^{13,26,27,32,33}. A characteristic peak at about 706.6 eV corresponding to ZVI ($\text{Fe}^0 2p_{3/2}$) confirmed the pres-

Fig. 3. XPS responses of synthesized nZVI.

ence of the metallic iron and others^{21,26,32} also reported the same findings.

The O 1s peak at 535.1 eV confirmed the binding of oxygen to surface iron^{16,26,33}. Since the XPS research depends on take-off angles of the particles and the XPS has sensitivities within 3 to 5 nm outer shells of the nZVI particles^{21,26,32}, the thickness of the outer shell in nZVI was at least less than 5 nm in the present study. In addition, Martin *et al.*³¹ estimated an average shell thickness in the range of 2.3–2.8 nm using XPS study.

Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM) study :

Surface morphologies of nZVI particles were examined by scanning electron microscopy analysis (SEM). Typical SEM image of nZVI particles (Fig. 4) indicated that the nanoparticles were uniform in size and shape

Fig. 4. SEM image of synthesized nZVI.

forming chain-like aggregates that could reach to several micrometers in length but were less than 100 nm in diameter.

The large surface area and magnetic dipole-dipole interactions of the individual particles caused aggregation of nanoparticles and thereafter chain-like aggregates^{5,10,22,27,34,35}. Phenrat *et al.*³⁶ reported that iron nanoparticles behaved as a ferromagnet once the size exceeded 15 nm which led to aggregation of the nanoparticles.

Energy-Dispersive X-Ray (EDS) study :

The energy-dispersive X-ray analysis (EDS) was performed at randomly selected areas on the solid surfaces to elucidate the atomic distribution on the surface of nZVI and elemental composition of solid materials²⁰. Fig. 5 showed that weight% of Fe and O in nZVI were 91.87 and 8.13 and atomic% of Fe and O in nZVI was 76.40 and 23.60. The result of this analysis suggested that Fe⁰ was pure and it did not contain any boron, carbon or sulphur as the expected contaminant from synthesis and analysis.

Fig. 5. EDS spectrum of nZVI.

Stability study by XRD :

The major challenge in nZVI research is its air stability due to prompt aerial oxidation to oxide/hydroxide shell^{5,37,38}. The nZVI synthesized in the present study was highly stable in ambient conditions kept inside a capped container to avoid dust contamination. Fig. 6 showed the XRD analysis result for a period of over 1 year. It is clear that the synthetic nZVI was in its zero valent state

Fig. 6. XRD patterns of fresh, 6 months old and 12 months old nZVI.

and no appearance of oxide/hydroxide shell formation was observed on the outer surfaces of the nZVI particles, whereas oxide shell was reported in the freshly synthesized nZVI by Choi *et al.* in their patent²¹. Others also reported the appearance of oxide/hydroxide shell after a few days during storage^{20,26,27,35,39}. The novelty of the present synthetic method was to control strictly oxidation of outer layer of nZVI nanoparticles since nZVI particles are highly sensitive to aerial oxidation and undergo spontaneously. Carefully oxidation of nZVI particles' outer layer was controlled during centrifugation, drying and pulverisation by maintaining inert condition and low temperature at 16–20 °C. Once a thin film of Fe-oxide was formed it acted as a protective coating to nZVI particles surfaces. We controlled the thickness of oxide layer within 3 nm in the present study which was confirmed by XPS and TEM analysis^{21,31}.

Adsorption study for removal of arsenic :

Separate sets of batch experiments were carried out to check performance of the synthesized nZVI for the removal of arsenite [As^{III}] and arsenate [As^V] as per the procedure mentioned in materials and methods. All experiments were repeated using commercial nZVI to compare its removal efficiency with our synthesized nZVI. Commercial nZVI had average particle size of 25 nm with specific surface area of 40–60 m²/g whereas our

synthetic nZVI particles had 83 m²/g of surface area by BET analysis. No special attempts were made to check speciation of arsenic after adsorption study, but all experiments were carried out inside glove box under N₂ atmosphere to avoid aerial oxidation of As^{III} to As^V 30,40,41. The concentrations of total arsenic in all aqueous samples were determined by ICP MS after filtration through a 0.22 μm Millipore filter paper. The results were expressed as mean of triplicate analyses with standard deviation (mean ± stdev, n = 3). Removal efficiencies of As^V and As^{III} were shown in Fig. 7A and Fig. 7B respectively.

Fig. 7. Removal efficiencies (in %) of As^V [A] and As^{III} [B] using commercial and synthetic nZVI particles.

The removal efficiency of As^V was increased with time by both synthesized and commercial nZVI as adsorbents (Fig. 7A). After 96 h of adsorption study removal efficiencies were 90.05% for commercial nZVI

and 95.10% for synthesized nZVI in the case of arsenate (Fig. 7A), whereas in the case of As^{III} 99.55% removal efficiency was observed for commercial and 99.53% for synthesized nZVI (Fig. 7B). The results of the adsorption study clearly showed that removal ability of synthetic nZVI was better than that of commercial one (As^{III} : 98% vs 89% by 4 h; As^V : 94% vs 71% by 4 h) and removal efficiency of As^{III} by the synthetic nZVI was greater than that of As^V (Fig. 7A and Fig. 7B). Guo *et al.*² reported the same findings in their report. In addition, nZVI were able to remove both As^{III} and As^V without prior chemical reduction which was supported by other literature⁴¹.

Conclusion :

Optimized method for synthesis of air stable nZVI is reported in the present work. It is possible to prepare air stable nZVI when complete synthesis is carried out in cold conditions i.e. at 16–20 °C. The size of nZVI is 30–40 nm with a BET surface area of 83 m²/g. Characterization of nZVI has shown that no appearance of oxide/hydroxide outer layer or no change in colour was observed after a period of one year. The important part of the present study is that no extra precaution need to be taken to preserve nZVI and the particles are stable in ambient conditions. Under anaerobic conditions (inside a glove box), adsorption studies has shown the removal efficiency of both As^{III} and As^V using the synthetic nZVI which is better than that of the commercial one. From these studies, it is confirmed that the removal efficiency is higher in the case of As^{III} in comparison to As^V. It is difficult to give insight on the basis of this preliminary study whether As^{III} was removed as such without oxidation to As^V or reduction to metallic arsenic using nZVI, but the results of this study has confirmed that the removal process is adsorptive rather than precipitative. More research is going on the interaction of As^{III} and As^V with nZVI in our laboratory for addressing the above issues.

Experimental

Reagents :

All chemicals used in this study were of analytical grade. Common chemicals such as FeCl₃, FeSO₄·7H₂O, HCl, etc. were collected from Sd fine-CHEM Ltd. (Mumbai, India). Important chemicals like As₂O₃, Na₂HAsO₄·7H₂O and NaBH₄ were purchased from Sigma Aldrich (St. Louis, MO, USA). Commercial nZVI was

collected from Shenzhen Junye Nano Material Co., Ltd., Guangdong-China. Deionised water was used throughout the experiment.

Synthesis of zero valent irons nano powder (nZVI) :

For the present study modified and optimized synthetic procedure of nZVI employed is given below briefly. Five grams of FeSO₄ was dissolved in 250 mL of 30% cold ethanol and was taken in a three necked round bottomed flask fitted with a propeller. About 1 g of NaBH₄ was dissolved in 25 mL of cold water and added to the Fe₂SO₄ solution dropwise (drop rate : 5 mL/min) by a peristaltic pump (Rivotek-India) with stirring at 600 rpm. In the present study deoxygenated water was used for preparing all the solutions throughout the experiments. During the synthesis reaction temperature was maintained at 16–20 °C. The solution slowly turned black and finally the black coloured particles were formed. The particles formed were centrifuged at 5000 rpm for 5 min. During centrifugation temperature was maintained at 16–20 °C, washed three times with absolute ethanol, dried in air for about 6 h and pulverised with spatula at 16 °C. After pulverisation, nZVI were stored at ambient condition (~25–40 °C) in a capped container to avoid dust contamination.

Characterization of synthetic nZVI :

The black coloured solid nZVI samples were characterized using powder XRD, SEM/EDS, TEM and XPS prior to adsorption experiments. Powder XRD analysis was carried out using Bruker D8 Advance Diffractometer (Bruker AXS, Germany) with Cu K α radiation ($\lambda = 1.54 \text{ \AA}$). XRD pattern of nZVI samples was recorded over a 2 θ range of 10–90°. SEM/EDS analysis was carried out using a Carl Zeiss SEM instrument attached to EVO MA 15 (Oxford Instrument). The solid samples were sprinkled on the adhesive carbon tape which was supported on a metallic disk. The sample surface images were taken at different magnifications. Simultaneously, EDS spectrum was recorded at selected areas on the solid surface to obtain the information on surface atomic distribution. Particle sizes of nZVI samples were determined by using TEM (Philips Tecnai-12, FEI, Netherlands) operating at an accelerated voltage of 100 kV, a magnification of 6,00,000x and a resolution of 2 Å. Sampling was done by dispersing nZVI in methanol using ultrasonic bath and

a drop of the dispersion was applied on Holey Carbon TEM Supported grid (Ernest Fullam, Inc., Latham, New York) to take images at different magnifications. Elemental speciation analysis was done by XPS (Thermo Fisher Scientific Multilab 2000, England) instrument with Al K α radiation of 1486.8 eV. The total arsenic content in all samples collected after adsorption study was determined by using ICP-MS (HP 4500 Yokogawa Analytical Systems, Hachioji, Japan). UV-Vis spectroscopic study (Shimadzu UV-Vis Spectrometer-1601, Japan) was carried out to observe the progress of reduction from ferrous to zero valent iron during preparation.

Batch test for adsorption study :

Batch test for adsorption of arsenic by nZVI was performed as described by Sasaki *et al.*²³. Separate batch experiments were carried out in triplicate for As^V and As^{III} with commercial nZVI and our synthesized nZVI respectively. In brief, one gram of nZVI was added to 50 mL of 100 ppm arsenite/or arsenate solution separately and pH was adjusted to 9.0 with 0.1 N NaOH. The mixtures were shaken at 50 rpm under room temperatures for 96 h by a rotospin-test tube rotor (Tarsons-India). At different time intervals 500 μ L solutions were taken and filtered using a micro filtration assembly (Millipore, Bedford, MA, USA) with 0.2 μ m membrane filter paper. All the batch experiments were carried out in an anaerobic glove box under N₂ atmosphere. After proper dilution total arsenic content of all samples were analyzed by ICP-MS.

Statistical analysis : All statistical analysis was done using StatView statistical software (StatView®, SAS Institute Inc., Second Edition, USA, 1998).

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